
Does Self-Efficacy Moderate The Effect of Workload on High School Teacher Burnout?

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ABSTRACT: Burnout is a state of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and decreased performance that will have a negative impact on ourselves and, of course, will also impact those around us. This study aimed to analyze the impact of workload on burnout among secondary school teachers and whether self-efficacy moderates the impact of workload on burnout. Burnout of high school teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic. The techniques used in this study are quantitative and explanatory in nature. The population of the study consisted of public high school teachers and the sample was 52 respondents. The sampling technique used is non-probability sampling. Data collection techniques include observation, interviews, questionnaires, etc. Data analysis techniques include simple linear regression analysis and relaxed regression analysis (MRA). Based on the results of our analysis, we know that workload has a positive and significant impact on secondary teacher burnout during the COVID-19 pandemic; and self-efficacy did not moderate the impact of workload on secondary teacher burnout during the COVID-19 pandemic.

KEYWORDS: Workload, Burnout, Self-Efficacy

INTRODUCTION

Burnout is a state of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduced performance that will have a negative impact on ourselves and of course, will also affect those around us where we work. According to Harison DF, the latest directory containing 2.46 publications related to burnout in European countries shows that health and social service workers experience the highest burnout at 43%, continuing followed by teachers (educators) at 32%, administrative and management staff at 9%, workers in the legal and police sectors at 4%, and other exhausted workers at 2%. Based on the above data, it can be seen that the teaching profession is the second level job with the most burnout (Harnida, 2015). This situation became even more severe when teachers faced the Covid-19 pandemic situation starting in early 2020 (Jomud et al., 2021; Marcionetti & Castelli, 2023; SzabO et al., 2022).

The Covid-19 virus epidemic has disrupted populations in various countries since the beginning of 2020 and has turned into a pandemic. This situation poses challenges for workers in many different sectors to continue operating safely, including teachers. In the field of education, changes have been made in the learning process to prevent the transmission of the Covid-19 virus. If previously learning took place in person, during the pandemic, learning takes place online through distance learning (PJJ). Teaching is one of the most stressful professions. As instructors and gatekeepers of the classroom, teachers often face emotionally powerful demands in the workplace. Over the past decade, teacher well-being has received widespread attention from scholars and practitioners; Teaching is a glorious profession but also full of difficulties. With long working hours and heavy workload, teachers easily fall into a state of exhaustion. Without adequate support, teachers risk becoming overwhelmed (Huang et al., 2019; SzabO et al., 2022).

Distance learning (PJJ) implemented by schools will certainly have a significant impact on the study habits implemented so far. Teachers, as the center of classroom learning, need to quickly change the online learning system provided they can understand and use information technology. Some of the IT facilities that can be used to support the distance learning (DLE) process are WhatsApp, Zoom, Google Meet, Google Class Room, video and online participation, as well as the use of media platforms. other convenience. process in schools.

Distance learning (PJJ) with the help of information technology allows flexibility in implementing the learning process, to always achieve learning goals. However, this flexibility does not reduce teacher burnout because there is pressure to increase teachers' workloads and each teacher's self-efficacy is not the same. This especially happens to teachers who do not understand and cannot use information technology in the learning process. Self-efficacy has been shown to be an important factor in behavioral outcomes in many contexts, including education. Teachers with higher self-efficacy tend to believe they are better able to manage their classrooms, motivate students, and help them learn better. Likewise, educational resources must be considered on

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a broader scale, including technological devices. Additionally, perceived support for autonomy, professional learning opportunities, and relationships with colleagues) and personal resources (e.g., adaptability, cognitive and behavioral adaptability as well as the implementation of personal capacity) (Ortan et al., 2021; Szabo et al., 2022).

Based on initial interviews with teachers, some signs indicate burnout, which are a feeling of hopelessness, a constant feeling of fatigue and lack of energy, a feeling of being stuck in work, and a lack of energy. motivation to work as usual. One of the causes of professional burnout is that teachers' workload changes and increases, both in quality and quantity, due to the implementation of a distance learning system (PJJ) that requires standardization. Equipment and implementation methods are different from direct learning. During the learning process, teachers use computers/laptops/smartphones instead of the classroom with a variety of applications, which also require teachers to look at the control screen for a relatively long time every day, from 3 to 5 hours per day. In addition to academic activities, teachers also have to perform administrative activities, which are again done online by attaching attachments proving their activities.

Teacher burnout is different, some of which is due to each teacher's self-efficacy. The results of the first interview conducted showed that there were two different views. First, the group of teachers believes that the online learning process using information technology applications is not a big problem. They believe that existing learning applications are not difficult to implement in their learning and administrative reporting, as part of their teaching duties. However, on the other hand, some teachers believe that this condition makes it difficult for them to confidently carry out learning tasks. Their inability and lack of skills and knowledge to use online learning applications is one of the reasons why they lose confidence.

From the results explained above, it can be seen that, during the Covid-19 pandemic, teachers' workload has changed and increased. If these teachers cannot adapt to change and are not confident in their ability to use information technology in their daily work, this will lead to increased burnout. This is consistent with the research results of Qin et al. (2022) that workload is a predictor of academic stress and burnout. Jomoad et al. (2021), from the results of their study, also demonstrated that a teacher assigned an increased workload is likely to experience burnout. There are times when a teacher's increased workload brings him honor and prestige. However, studies show that increased workload leads to exhaustion and stress.

Furthermore, it was also determined that individual self-efficacy can strengthen or weaken the impact of workload on teacher burnout. Consistent with the findings of Huang et al., (2019) dan Smith, (2019), teacher self-efficacy was negatively related to anxiety and depression and positively related to anxiety and depression. extreme enthusiasm and satisfaction. This study shows that teachers' self-efficacy has a positive impact on their health. This study aims to analyze the causal relationship between workload and burnout among secondary school teachers, as well as analyze whether self-efficacy moderates the causal relationship between workload work and burnout of middle school teachers.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The relationship between workload and burnout

Burnout is characterized by emotional exhaustion, feelings of detachment (depersonalization), and feelings of low personal accomplishment (Johnson et al., 2020). The teaching profession involves meeting a variety of professional needs, which often gives the impression of a heavy workload. Other examples of work demands are the many meetings that hinder preparation time, the administrative paperwork created by management, and is subject to constant reforms and changes that require reorganization of work. work and tasks. Nearly half of the teachers surveyed said increased administrative duties had increased their workload. Therefore, the high workload is not related to teaching itself but to the constant increase of new requirements being added without eliminating other job duties. Teachers say they face new technology systems, new demands for long-term educational planning to align teaching with goals, and new demands for grading and assessment of learning outcomes. Teachers have many things to do, their attention is divided into many tasks and they also consider many things such as teaching unmotivated students, maintaining discipline in the classroom, and dealing with general academic pressure (Arvidsson et al., 2019).

Too much pressure will lead to burnout due to not being able to meet job requirements. The teaching profession in Sweden reports high levels of symptoms related to stress and burnout compared to other professions. Sometimes teacher burnout has a negative impact on teaching. Teachers are stressed due to the workload of planning lessons, organizing activities, developing curriculum, managing extracurricular activities, monitoring classrooms, giving feedback, maintaining discipline, and paying salaries. Research has shown that there are many causes of stress and problems for teachers, such as teaching unmotivated students, maintaining discipline, time and workload constraints, managing change, evaluation by others, relationships with colleagues, self-esteem and status, management, and administration. Stress in the teaching profession is an international phenomenon that has a negative impact on both teachers and the quality of education (Jomoad et al., 2021).

The teaching profession involves meeting a variety of professional requirements, often leading to the perception of a heavy workload. Other examples of work demands are the many meetings that hinder preparation time, the administrative paperwork created by management, and being subject to constant reforms and changes that require reorganization job and job duties. Nearly half of the teacher group surveyed said the increase in administrative tasks had added to their workload. Therefore, the high

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workload is not related to teaching itself but to the constant increase of new demands added without eliminating other work tasks (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2016).

Work overload is one of the causes of burnout in teachers, leading to a decrease in physical and mental energy. Factors that contribute to burnout may include longer teaching hours and the need for ideal conditions that the workplace may not be able to provide. Teachers at Mahayag South Primary School are exhausted from work overload. However, they still perform their respective functions. No matter how tired they feel, they always try their best to perform their duties; Therefore, their performance is very satisfactory (Jomuad et al., 2021)

Teachers are stressed due to their workload when planning lessons, organizing activities, developing curriculum, managing extracurricular activities, supervising classrooms, giving feedback, maintaining discipline, and compensating students. Compensate for teacher shortages, teacher absences, record keeping, class schedule management, and evaluation. and evaluate student learning outcomes, in addition to motivating students through words and actions. Teachers say they face new technology systems, new needs for long-term educational planning to align teaching with goals, and new needs for grading and assessment of student outcomes. students as well as extensive individual development plans for each student with increasing time pressures. This is seen as leading to unplanned changes in schedules and higher workloads. (Desouky & Allam, 2017).

H1: Workloads affect burnout

Self-Efficacy Moderates the Effect of Workload on Burnout

Self-efficacy is based on Bandura's social cognitive theory and Rotter's internal and external control theory. Rotter clarifies that self-efficacy will increase if teachers believe that student success is influenced by their interventions and will decrease if student success and actions are due to external factors. outside. Bandura also emphasized that self-efficacy is the ability to regulate one's actions, impulses, and thoughts as influenced by the synergistic relationship between the individual's behavior and his or her environment. Through self-efficacy, people create an impact in what they do through preventive behavior, self-organization, self-reflection, and self-regulation (Fabelico & Afalla, 2020).

University professors have high levels of self-confidence and self-efficacy, moderate levels of burnout, and highly satisfactory teaching results, regardless of age, gender, marital status, number of dependents, educational level, seniority, teaching status, and educational level. places. Teacher levels of competence, self-efficacy, and performance were comparable according to teacher characteristics, while teacher burnout levels varied according to the number of people in charge. Teachers with two or fewer dependents tend to be more emotionally exhausted than teachers with more than two dependents. Teachers with advanced education demonstrated great courage. A high level of persistence in a teacher's actions influences a high level of teacher confidence in meeting needs, inspiring students, and responding to change. Although teacher learning outcomes were not influenced by persistence, self-efficacy, and burnout, teacher learning outcomes were better predicted by subject knowledge learning and learning management (Fabelico & Afalla, 2020).

Research conducted by Johnson et al., (2020) found that the risk of stress was nearly three times higher in healthcare workers with low self-esteem, and participants experiencing stress were three times more likely to experience burnout. Studies among Polish and Dutch nurses and healthcare professionals in Spain have also demonstrated that low self-esteem and work stress are significantly associated with burnout. Low self-esteem can lead to psychological effects that make a person more susceptible to stressful situations. Another aspect of the connection between stress and self-esteem is that insecurity is one of the common effects of low self-esteem. This can become a vicious cycle in which low self-esteem causes a person to take on more work than they can actually handle. This, in turn, leads to increased stress. Although low self-esteem is independently related to burnout, burnout is also a consequence in workers who experience high levels of stress on the job. This relationship pathway was clearly illustrated in the present study, where low self-esteem had a direct effect on burnout, as well as an indirect effect through the mediating variable (stress). A similar model using standardized path coefficients was demonstrated in an Italian study, in which high workload led to burnout with job control as the mediating variable. This is consistent with the study of Matos et al. (2022), their results also indicate that teacher self-efficacy is a direct positive predictor of personal achievement in burnout, a dimension that brings together the motivational factors, satisfaction, and positive evaluation at work.

However, another study conducted by Marcionetti & Castelli (2023) in its model found that: teachers' self-efficacy does not directly influence the perception of workload. Hence, Swiss teachers' efficacy beliefs can surely influence their choice of activities, the effort they expend on an activity, and how long they will persevere when facing obstacles; however, those beliefs are less likely to affect their perception of workload. This is in line with the results of research from Harnida (2015) that the relationship between self-efficacy and burnout in nurses in this study is not proven or rejected, meaning that the high and low self-efficacy of a nurse does not absolutely affect the occurrence of burnout in nurses. This finding is not in line with the hypothesis proposed, that the lower the nurse's self-efficacy, the higher the burnout experienced. This is not in line with the findings of descriptive data found when burnout seen from each aspect was found with a moderate level of self-efficacy, burnout experienced by nurses was burnout at a low level with an Emotional Exhaustion aspect in the low category of 85% and the Personalized category in the category This finding makes it clear that the burnout criteria are low if the emotional exhaustion and personalized

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aspects are low and the personal accomplishment aspects are high. Therefore, in this study, there was no burnout related to nurses' self-efficacy.

H2: Self-efficacy moderates the effect of workload on burnout

The Empirical Model

The empirical model of this study is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Empirical Model

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is a quantitative approach using the explanatory research method, which aims to determine how the effect of workload on burnout with self-efficacy as a moderation variable in public high school 4 Banjarmasin teachers during the Covid-19 pandemic. The unit of analysis in this study was a teacher of public high school 4 Banjarmasin. As for census sampling, all 52 teachers were used as respondents.

The data collection techniques used are observation and interviews aimed at initial data collection. Next, questionnaires are used to answer research problems. The analysis technique used in this study used Simple Linear Regression and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). The following is the operational definition of the research variables used in this study:

Table 1. Variable Operational Definition

Variable	Indikator	Items	Source
Burnout (Y)	Emotional exhaustion	Emotionally drained from work	(Maslach et al., 2009)
	Depersonalization	Refers to negative responses	
	Diminished personal achievement	Decreased feeling of competence of a person	
Workload (X)	Targets to be achieved	The targets achieved are clear	(Shah et al., 2011)
	Working conditions	Feelings towards the work environment	
	Standards of work	A feeling that is up to standard	
Self-efficacy (M)	Level	A person's confidence in completing the difficulty level of the task	(Fabelico & Afalla, 2020)
	Generality	Able to do a variety of jobs in a wide and varied scope	
	strength	Strong one's beliefs about one's abilities	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

This study aims to analyze how the effect of workload on burnout with self-efficacy as a moderation variable in high school 4 Banjarmasin teachers during the Covid-19 pandemic. From the results of data analysis of the responses of 52 respondents, the characteristics of respondents can be described as follows:

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Figure 2. Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

Figure 3. Characteristics of Respondents by Age Range

Figure 4. Characteristics of Respondents by Education Level

Figure 5. Characteristics of Respondents by Length of Work

Validity Test Results

The results of the validity test are carried out by comparing r_{value} with r_{table} , where the requirement to meet the validity criteria is that the instrument item must have a $r_{\text{value}} > r_{\text{table}}$ with a significance of 5%.

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Table 2. Workload Variable Validity Test Results

Items	R _{value}	r _{Table}	Sig	Information
X1	0,686	0,268	0,000	Valid
X2	0,584	0,268	0,000	Valid
X3	0,560	0,268	0,000	Valid
X4	0,698	0,268	0,000	Valid
X5	0,713	0,268	0,000	Valid
X6	0,754	0,268	0,000	Valid
X7	0,857	0,268	0,000	Valid
X8	0,562	0,268	0,000	Valid
X9	0,529	0,268	0,000	Valid
X10	0,710	0,268	0,000	Valid
X11	0,770	0,268	0,000	Valid
X12	0,747	0,268	0,000	Valid

Table 2 shows that all items in question on workload variables are valid. This can be seen from the r_{value} which is greater than the r_{table} , which is 0.268 with a significance of less than 5%. This means that all question items on this questionnaire can measure workload variables.

Table 3. Burnout Variable Validity Test Results

Items	R _{value}	R _{table}	Sig	Information
Y1	0,805	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y2	0,759	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y3	0,763	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y4	0,791	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y5	0,699	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y6	0,730	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y7	0,733	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y8	0,698	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y9	0,693	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y10	0,726	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y11	0,737	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y12	0,713	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y13	0,701	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y14	0,718	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y15	0,510	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y16	0,650	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y17	0,660	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y18	0,522	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y19	0,540	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y20	0,696	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y21	0,619	0,268	0,000	Valid
Y22	0,608	0,268	0,000	Valid

Table 3 shows that all items in question on the burnout variable are valid. This can be seen from the r_{value} which is greater than the r_{table} , which is 0.268 with a significance of less than 5%. This means that all question items on this questionnaire can measure burnout variables.

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Table 4. Self-efficacy variable validity test results

Items	R _{value}	R _{table}	Sig	Information
M1	0,774	0,268	0,000	Valid
M2	0,746	0,268	0,000	Valid
M3	0,640	0,268	0,000	Valid
M4	0,668	0,268	0,000	Valid
M5	0,770	0,268	0,000	Valid
M6	0,704	0,268	0,000	Valid
M7	0,798	0,268	0,000	Valid
M8	0,781	0,268	0,000	Valid
M9	0,737	0,268	0,000	Valid
M10	0,747	0,268	0,000	Valid

Table 4 shows that all items in question on the self-efficacy variable were valid. This can be seen from the r_{value} which is greater than the r_{table} , which is 0.268 with a significance of less than 5%. This means that all question items on this questionnaire can measure the variable self-efficacy.

Reliability Test Results

The results of the reliability test are carried out by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (α) coefficient value, where the requirement to meet the reliable criteria is that the construct or variable of the instrument has a Cronbach Alpha (α) coefficient value of > 0.70 .

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
Workload (X)	0,892	Reliable
Burnout (Y)	0,945	Reliable
Self-Efficacy (M)	0,902	Reliable

Table 5 shows the results of reliability tests related to statement items of all variables, namely workload (X), burnout (Y), and self-efficacy (Y) declared reliable, judging from Cronbach's Alpha value of > 0.70 . This shows that indicators of the workload variable (X) produce consistent data against the burnout variable (Y) and the self-efficacy variable (M) as moderation variables.

Classical Assumption Test Results

Normality Test

Table 6. Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		standardized Residual
N		52
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	15,14976420
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,112
	Positive	,069
	Negative	-,112
Test Statistic		,112
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,128 ^c
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		

Table 6 shows the Asymp values. Sig 0.128, where the value is greater than the significance value of 0.05. This means that residual data is normally distributed.

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Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 7. Heteroscedasticity Test Results with Glejser Test

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-,028	,117		-,238	,813
	Beban Kerja	,004	,002	,219	1,489	,143
	Self-Efficacy	,001	,002	,041	,280	,780

a. Dependent Variable: ABS_RES1

Table 7 shows that there were no symptoms of heteroscedasticity or passed the test, where the significance value in the workload variable was 0.143 > the significance value was 5%. Furthermore, the significance value on the self-efficacy variable is 0.143 > a significance value of 5%. From the results, it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity did not occur in this study.

Multicolonicity Test

Table 8. Multicolonicity Test Results

Variables	Tolerance	VIF	Information
Workload (X)	0,891	1,122	No multicolonicity occurs
Self-Efficacy (M)	0,891	1,122	No multicolonicity occurs

Table 8 shows that the tolerance value in each variable > 0.10 and the VIF value in each variable also shows < 10. From these results it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicolonicity between independent variables.

Linearity Test

Table 9. Linearity Test Results

Dependent Variables	Independent Variables and Moderation	Sig. Deviation Form Linearity	Information
Burnout	Workload (X)	0,085	Linear
	Self-Efficacy (M)	0,687	Linear

Table 9 shows that workload variables have sig values. Deviation Form Line of 0.085 > 0.05, and Sig value. The deviation form linearity for the moderation variable self-efficacy was 0.687 > 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that the value obtained from each variable indicates a linear value between workload against burnout and self-efficacy as a moderation variable.

Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Table 10. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Variables	Regression Coefficient	tvalue	Sig.	Information
Constant	21,496			
Workload (X)	1,078	3,182	0,003	Significant
R			0,410	
R Square			0,168	
Std. Error of the Estimate			17,387	
Adjusted R Square			0,152	

Table 10 shows that the workload regression coefficient (X) is 1.078 with a significance value of 0.003. This shows that the workload variable is positive and significant, which means that the workload variable (X) has a contributing and unidirectional influence on the burnout variable (Y).

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Moderated Regression Analysis Test (MRA)

Table 11. Moderated Regression Analysis Test Results (MRA)

Variables	Regression Coefficient	t _{hitung}	Sig.	Information
Constant	74,371			
Zscore: Workload (X)	4,861	2,105	0,041	Significant
Zscore: Self-Efficacy (M)	9,300	3,599	0,001	Significant
Absolute Difference	1,829	0,551	0,584	No Significant

Table 11 shows that the workload variable regression coefficient value of 4.861 has a significant value of 0.041 ($0.041 < 0.05$), which can be concluded that the workload variable has a significant influence on burnout. The regression coefficient value of the self-efficacy variable of 9.300 has a significant value of 0.001 ($0.001 < 0.05$), which can be concluded that the self-efficacy variable has a significant influence on burnout. Furthermore, based on the regression coefficient of the absolute difference value variable of 1.829 with a significance of 0.584 ($0.584 > 0.05$), it can be concluded that the self-efficacy variable does not moderate the effect between workloads on burnout.

The hypothesis Test

Table 12. Test Results t and MRA

Variables	T _{value}	t _{table}	Sig.
Workload	3,182	2,00958	0,003
Absolute Value Difference	0,551	2,00958	0,584

Table 12 shows that the workload variable (X), has a calculated value of $t_{table} > (3.182 > 2.00958)$ with a significance value of 0.003. So that it can be concluded that Hypothesis 1 is accepted, namely that workload affects the burnout of high school teachers during the Covid-19 pandemic. While the self-efficacy variable (M), has a t_{value} of $t_{table} < (0.551 < 2.00958)$ with a significance value of 0.584. So it can be concluded that Hypothesis 2 is rejected, namely that self-efficacy does not moderate the effect between workload on burnout of high school teachers during the Covid-19 pandemic.

DISCUSSION

The effect of Workload on Burnout

The results of research that has been conducted using the t test, it was found that there was a positive and significant influence of workload (X) on Burnout (Y) of public high school teachers 4 Banjarmasin during the Covid-19 pandemic.

From respondents' responses about how workload and burnout are related, it can be seen that the level of workload itself is felt by teachers is relatively low. This is because respondents perceive that the workload they get is something they should do as part of a teacher's duties. However, when viewed from respondents' responses to the burnout conditions they experienced, it turned out that respondents perceived that the burnout conditions experienced were relatively high. This is because although teachers understand their duties and functions as teachers, the Covid-19 pandemic has brought significant changes to the way they complete work. This new method, without sufficient preparation in terms of both time and material and methods puts physical and mental pressure on teachers every time they prepare and carry out their duties.

These results are consistent with research conducted by Jomoad et al. (2021), Skaalvik & Skaalvik (2016) and Desouky & Allam (2017) that too much pressure will lead to burnout due to the inability to respond to needs work. Work overload is one of the causes of burnout in teachers, leading to a decrease in physical and mental energy. Factors contributing to burnout may include longer teaching hours and the need for ideal conditions that the workplace may not be able to provide.

Self-Efficacy Moderates the Effect of Workload on Burnout

The results of research that has been conducted using the Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) test found that self-efficacy (M) does not moderate the effect between workload (X) and burnout (Y) of public high school teachers 4 Banjarmasin during the Covid-19 pandemic.

The results of the analysis showed that self-efficacy was not able to moderate the effect between workload and teacher burnout. Self-efficacy has a relatively low value, does not have a significant impact due to the perception of teachers that every assignment they get is a condition that they should carry out in accordance with their duties and functions as a teacher. This relatively low self-efficacy is also partly due to the absence of programs to support teachers in adapting to changes in teaching methods and methods from normal times to the Covid-19 pandemic.

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However, on the other hand, the burnout of high school teachers is still relatively high, one of which is caused by these different teaching methods and methods. So that when teachers carry out their work, there are many difficulties, because every work is carried out on various applications based on information technology and is carried out online, and all of these are new knowledge and abilities that cannot be fully mastered. This raises concerns of inability to achieve the performance that has been set.

These results are consistent with the research conducted by Marcionetti & Castelli (2023) and Harnida (2015) in their model, showing that teachers' self-efficacy does not directly influence the perception of workload jobs. The relationship between self-efficacy and burnout among nurses in this study was neither proven nor disproven, which means a nurse's high or low self-efficacy does not completely affect the manifestation of professional burnout in nurses.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study show that workload has an effect on high school teacher burnout. The effect of workload on high school teachers' burnout was not moderated by their self-efficacy. With these findings, school management should be able to make a real contribution in preparing to improve the ability of high school teachers to face obstacles faced in carrying out tasks during the Covid-19 pandemic, such as training on the use of information technology-based applications. With this increase in ability, it is expected that the self-efficacy of high school teachers will also increase, which in turn will contribute positively to the performance of teachers by minimizing the burnout conditions they experience.

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